

Data Governance Plan for the Malawi Energy Access Project

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Acknowledgements.....	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1.0 INTRODUCTION.....	5
1.1 Background.....	5
1.2 Purpose and Scope	5
1.3 Objective and Aim.....	5
2.0 METHODOLOGY	5
2.1 Modelling Approach/Tool Implemented.....	5
2.2 Data Sources	6
2.3 Assumptions	6
3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	6
3.1 Data Governance Framework.....	6
3.1.1 <i>Data Governance Structure</i>	6
3.2 Governance Policies and Standards	9
3.2.1 <i>Data Quality Standards</i>	9
3.3 Compliance and Regulations	10
3.4 Database Design.....	10
3.4.1 <i>Data Model</i>	10
3.4.2 <i>Storage Requirements</i>	10
3.4.3 <i>Data Backup and Recovery</i>	11
3.4.4 <i>Data Access and User Levels</i>	11
3.5 <i>Data Processing and Integration</i>	11
3.6 <i>Data Security and Risk Management</i>	11
3.6.1 <i>Data Security Measures</i>	11
3.6.2 <i>Risk Management</i>	12
3.7 <i>Data Sharing and Publication</i>	12
3.7.1 <i>Data Sharing Policies</i>	12
3.7.2 <i>Metadata and Documentation</i>	12
3.8 Sustainability and Continuous Improvement	12
3.8.1 <i>Sustainability Plan</i>	12
3.8.2 <i>Continuous Improvement</i>	12
4.0 CONCLUSION AND POLICY INSIGHTS	13
5.0 REFERENCES	14
6.0 APPENDICES	15
6.1 <i>Appendix 1: Roles and Responsibilities</i>	15
6.2 <i>Appendix 2: Entity Diagram Description</i>	16
6.3 <i>Appendix 3: Risk and Mitigation Strategies</i>	19

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Malawi Energy Access Project Data Governance Plan outlines a comprehensive framework to support the efficient collection, management, sharing, and use of energy-related data. This framework is essential for driving evidence-based policy decisions and ensuring that Malawi's energy access goals are met effectively. The plan provides guidelines for data governance structures, data quality management, data security, and stakeholder collaboration.

An assessment of the current status of energy data governance approaches found that fragmented data systems; capacity gaps; inadequate coordination; data quality challenges and limited use are the key issues that need to be addressed for the successful implementation of the energy data governance plan.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Access to energy is a critical component of national development. In Malawi, expanding energy access is central to achieving the country's broader socio-economic goals of poverty reduction, improved public health, and enhanced economic productivity (Government of Malawi, 2018). Despite having implemented several programmes and projects, a significant portion of Malawi's population still lacks access to electricity and clean cooking solutions, particularly in rural areas with the overall access currently at 26% (National Statistics Office, 2024). Compilation of national energy access statistics has relied on national census data and sample surveys which may not depict the true energy picture of energy access.

1.2 Purpose and Scope

The Data Governance Plan for the Malawi Energy Access Project establishes a structured framework to manage, share and utilise energy data effectively in implementing energy access projects across the country.

The plan covers all energy data in the country from Ministries, Departments and Agencies, national utilities, independent power producers, off-grid energy companies and local councils. The main data sets are on energy access, consumption, and income levels for all energy users in all districts in Malawi. However, the data does not include the national electricity network including transmission and distribution constraints.

1.3 Objective and Aim

The objective of the plan is to ensure that data related to energy access, energy consumption, energy investments and related infrastructure is accurate, secure, and available for energy modelling, policy analysis, project conceptualisation and informed decision-making. The plan aims to support tracking energy policy goals, including increasing access to electricity and clean cooking in the country.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Modelling Approach/Tool Implemented

The data governance framework is designed to support energy access modelling using tools such as onSSET and OnStove which require high-quality geospatial and demographic data. These tools help to simulate various scenarios for electrification and clean cooking initiatives. A database which will follow a relational model was designed to track energy access by households in all districts in Malawi. The database will be essential for tracking the country's energy access progress and reporting on sustainable development goal number seven on universal access to energy.

2.2 Data Sources

Primary data for household electricity connections and cooking uses in all districts of Malawi will mainly be collected through field surveys using GPS devices and mobile phones with MerginMaps and QGIS as software for interacting and integrating the data into the geospatial platform (Bauer, 2021). Remote sensing will complement the collection of geospatial data.

Secondary data will be collected from the Ministry of Energy; National Statistics Office; Electricity Supply Corporation of Malawi Limited; off-grid energy companies; and energy associations. Open sources data platforms and websites for international organisations will be used to supplement secondary data.

2.3 Assumptions

The data governance plan will follow and abide by the following quality standards:

- Availability of up-to-date and accurate data from government and third-party sources
- Regular validation against field data and independent sources is to be carried out.
- Data entries should follow standardised formats, units of measurement and codes
- Cross-system and temporal consistency checks to ensure uniformity across datasets.
- All required data fields should be filled with minimal missing data
- Regular audits are to be undertaken to identify and address gaps in the data
- Data updates should occur on a quarterly basis and also be promptly updated following any significant changes or developments

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Data Governance Framework

3.1.1 Data Governance Structure

3.1.1.1 Data Governance Working Group

The Ministry will form a data governance working group which will oversee the development and operationalisation of the energy access data platform. The working group will be chaired by the Ministry and will be composed of members from the institutions as shown in the table below with the representatives selected based on their expertise:

Table 1: Data Governance Working Group Membership

Institution	Responsibility
Ministry of Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Lead the committee in overseeing the platform’s development and operationalization ➤ Facilitate coordination between all stakeholders and ensure effective communication ➤ Provide data for Rural Electrification
Electricity Supply Corporation of Malawi (ESCOM) Limited	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Provide data on grid connections and system reliability ➤ Validate and ensure the accuracy of energy access data
National Planning Commission (NPC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Utilise platform data for national development planning ➤ Ensure data quality meets national standards
Malawi Energy Regulatory Authority (MERA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Oversee regulatory compliance for data governance ➤ Engage stakeholders to address data gaps
Renewable Energy Industry Association of Malawi (REIAMA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Facilitate data provision from renewable energy companies
Department of ICT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Lead platform development and maintenance ➤ Establish and enforce data security protocols ➤ Ensure interoperability with other national databases ➤ Provide training for platform users
National Cookstoves Steering Committee (NCSC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Contribute data on clean cooking initiatives and use programs ➤ Coordinate with NGOs and the private sector for data coverage
Malawi University of Business and Applied Science (MUBAS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Support innovation for the platform ➤ Validate data compliance with quality standards

3.1.1.2 Roles and Responsibilities

The Ministry of Energy will appoint a Data Steward who will be responsible for overseeing the energy access platform and ensuring compliance with national standards. Data Custodians from the ICT department will manage the data's technical infrastructure, while planners, policy-makers and other key stakeholders will access and use the data for energy modelling, decision and policy-making. Technical divisions of the Ministry of Energy, ESCOM and Off-grid Energy Companies will provide the required data on-grid and off-grid electricity connection and cooking energy devices. A detailed description of the roles and responsibilities is provided in Appendix 1.

3.2 Governance Policies and Standards

3.2.1 Data Quality Standards

The data governance plan will follow and abide by the quality standards stipulated in the table below (European Commission, 2020).

Table 2: Data Quality Standards

Accuracy	<p>All data should accurately reflect grid and off-grid electricity connections, cooking energy usage, and other relevant metrics and should not have a deviation of more than 5%.</p> <p>Regular validation against field data and independent sources is to be carried out.</p>
Consistency	<p>Data entries should follow standardised formats, units of measurement and codes as provided in Electricity By-laws 2016</p> <p>Cross-system and temporal consistency checks to ensure uniformity across datasets.</p>
Completeness	<p>All required data fields should be filled with minimal missing data</p> <p>Regular audits to be undertaken to identify and address gaps in the data</p>
Timeliness	<p>Data updates should occur on a quarterly basis and be promptly updated following any significant changes or developments</p> <p>Only data collected within the last year will be eligible</p>

3.3 Compliance and Regulations

To ensure compliance with the legal framework, the data governance plan will adhere to the Constitution of Malawi, the Electronics & Cybersecurity Act 2016 (Presidential Delivery Unit, 2022) and align with the personal data protection GDPR standards for managing personal data. The Energy Act of 2004, will be the overall guiding legal framework for all energy access data.

3.4 Database Design

3.4.1 Data Model

A database shown in Figure 1 was designed to track energy access by households in all districts in Malawi. Appendix 2 provides tables with the datasets together with unique identifiers on the type of electricity systems used by households including the Main-grid and off grid solutions such as Solar Home Systems, Mini-grid and Diesel Generator. The cooking system will include an electricity cooker, Liquified Petroleum Gas (LPG) stove, Biogas Stove, Ethanol Stove, Improved Cookstoves and traditional cookstoves. The use of geographic data enables the database to support spatial queries for mapping and analysis purposes (Korkovelos *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 1: Database Schema

3.4.2 Storage Requirements

The database is expected to take up large volumes of both spatial and non-spatial data. Storage requirements for each field including overheads will therefore be calculated to provide for enough total storage to ensure optimal performance.

3.4.3 Data Backup and Recovery

To ensure database system resilience to data loss and efficient data recovery in times of emergency, a full backup will be done every week with incremental and differential daily and two times per week, respectively. The backups will be stored both on-site, offsite and cloud. Data recovery strategy will conform to Recovery Time Objectives (RTO) of 4 hours and Recovery Point Objectives (RPO) of 1.

3.4.4 Data Access and User Levels

The database will have three user and access levels. The head of the ICT department in the Ministry of Energy will be the administrator and will have full access. Designated Officers in the Electricity and Research and Development Directorates will be editors, while all other stakeholders and the general public will be read-only users of the database.

A two-factor authentication system will be put in place as a security measure for accessing the database and all public users will be required to register and provide the reason for accessing the system and access credentials will be provided upon verification and approval.

3.5 Data Processing and Integration

The data will be subjected to a multi-step cleaning process, involving outlier detection, conversion of units to the metric system, and cross-referencing with national data from the national statistics office or validation

The database is expected to be integrated with other existing databases, such as the Integrated Energy Planning tool and the National Energy Information System. To ensure interoperability, the Metadata of these systems will be aligned, and the datasets will be converted to Common Formats and Standards such as GeoJSON and XML (Fhwa, 2015).

3.6 Data Security and Risk Management

3.6.1 Data Security Measures

A mix of encryption, access controls, and network security measures will provide a comprehensive approach to securing data and systems. By encrypting data at rest and in transit, implementing strict Role Based Access Control (RBAC) policies, and securing the network through firewalls, VPNs, IDS/IPS, and segmentation, the Ministry will protect the database against a wide range of threats and ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the data. Regular updates, monitoring, and adherence to best practices will be undertaken to keep maintaining and improving the security protocols.

Encryption keys will be managed centrally by the IT department, with strict protocols in place to prevent unauthorised access.

3.6.2 Risk Management

A risk assessment identified potential threats across cybersecurity, operational, and legal domains. Mitigation strategies outlined in Appendix 3 will be undertaken, regularly reviewed and updated to protect the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of the data and ensure compliance with relevant standards.

3.7 Data Sharing and Publication

3.7.1 Data Sharing Policies

Energy access data will be made available under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International License, allowing free use for non-commercial purposes.

Data will be published annually on the energy access database in both CSV and GeoJSON formats, to ensure accessibility for both technical and non-technical users. GeoNode will be the main platform for data sharing and ISO 19100 series of standards will be followed.

3.7.2 Metadata and Documentation

All geospatial data will be documented according to ISO 19115 standards, including detailed descriptions of data sources, methods, and accuracy.

A version control system will be implemented to track all changes to datasets, ensuring that updates are logged, and older versions can be accessed if necessary.

3.8 Sustainability and Continuous Improvement

3.8.1 Sustainability Plan

The Ministry of Energy will provide financial resources for database maintenance and updates in the annual budget which will be supplemented by funds from development partners who are implementing energy access projects in the country.

The Ministry of Energy will assign dedicated officers from the technical directorates to work hand in hand with the IT division in managing the database. Continuous training will be provided to this team to ensure they remain knowledgeable about data governance practices and tools.

3.8.2 Continuous Improvement

Every month, the Quality Assurance department will monitor and audit the database. Annual surveys and stakeholder engagement meetings will be conducted for stakeholders to provide feedback and suggestions on the data governance framework. The feedback will be used to make informed improvements and adjustments to the system.

Training Sessions on data management best practices, emerging technologies, and changes in regulatory requirements will be conducted quarterly focussing on data stewards and users of the database.

The database management team will regularly conduct online and physical workshops where stakeholders will share knowledge on how to manage and use the database, discuss challenges on the database, share best practices, and explore new developments which can improve the platform.

4.0 CONCLUSION AND POLICY INSIGHTS

The Data Governance Plan is critical to achieving Malawi's energy access objectives as it will enhance data management, support evidence-based decision-making, and contribute to sustainable energy development. To achieve this, the Government should develop a National Policy on Energy Data; designate a centralized data management body for energy and strengthen the capacity of government staff and other stakeholders in energy data management, analysis, and cybersecurity.

The Data Governance Plan provided the following insights on the project:

- Informed the project of the need for complete data sets to avoid gaps
- The need to preserve data integrity across different stages of the project
- Informed the project of the importance of consistency when integrating data from multiple sources
- Provided clarity on who is responsible for data management, quality control, and decision-making processes
- The project must comply with relevant data protection regulations and standards

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6.0 APPENDICES

6.1 Appendix 1: Roles and Responsibilities

Role	Responsibility
Administrator (Data Steward)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Appointed by the Ministry of Energy. ❖ Full control over the database platform ❖ Manage user access and permissions ❖ Ensure compliance with national data standards and policies
Database Manager (Data Custodian)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Manage the technical infrastructure of the database. ❖ Oversee data storage, security, and backups. ❖ Ensure data integrity and system performance.
Analysts (Planners and Policy-makers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Data editors ❖ Access and query the database for energy data. ❖ Analyze data for energy modelling and forecasting. ❖ Use data to support decision-making and policy development.
Data Providers (Technical Divisions, ESCOM, Offgrid Energy Companies)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Input, update, and maintain data on grid and off-grid electricity connections. ❖ Provide data on cooking energy usage. Ensure data accuracy and timeliness.
Registered Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Viewing data ❖ Data upload and Analysis
Public Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Viewing data

6.2 Appendix 2: Entity Diagram Description

Entity	Attribute	Description
Household	<p>HouseholdID (PK)</p> <p>access_status (ENUM)</p> <p>income_level (ENUM)</p> <p>geomGEOMETRY(POINT, 4326)</p>	<p>Represents a household in a particular district</p> <p>HouseholdID: Unique identifier for the household</p> <p>access_status: Enum for access to energy services</p> <p>income_level: Enum for income categories for each household</p> <p>district_id: Foreign key linking to the District entity</p> <p>geom: Spatial data representing the geographic point location of the household</p>
District	<p>district_id (PK)</p> <p>name (TEXT)</p> <p>population (INT)</p> <p>geom (GEOMETRY (POLYGON, 4326))</p>	<p>Represents a district in the database</p> <p>district_id: Unique identifier for the district.</p> <p>name: Name of the district</p> <p>population: Population size of the district</p> <p>geom: Spatial data representing the geographic boundaries (polygon) of the district.</p>

Entity	Attribute	Description
Electricity System	<p>electricity_system_id (PK)</p> <p>installation_date (DATE)</p> <p>system_type (VARCHAR)</p>	<p>Represents an electricity system installed in a household</p> <p>electricity_system_id: Unique identifier for the electricity system.</p> <p>installation_date: Date the system was installed.</p> <p>system_type: Type of electricity system (solar home system, minigrid, generator or grid,).</p>
Cooking System	<p>cooking_system_id (PK)</p> <p>system_type (VARCHAR)</p> <p>installation_date (DATE)</p>	<p>Represents a cooking system used in a household</p> <p>cooking_system_id: Unique identifier for the cooking system.</p> <p>system_type: Type of cooking system (electricity cooker, Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) stove, Biogas Stove, Ethanol Stove, Improved Cookstoves and traditional cookstoves).</p> <p>installation_date: Date the cooking system was installed.</p>

Entity	Attribute	Description
Household_Electricity_System	<p>household_id (FK)</p> <p>electricity_system_id (FK)</p>	<p>Represents the many-to-many relationship between households and electricity systems.</p> <p>household_id: Foreign key linking to the Household entity.</p> <p>electricity_system_id: Foreign key linking to the Electricity_System entity</p>
Household_Cooking_System	<p>household_id (FK)</p> <p>cooking_system_id (FK)</p>	<p>Represents the many-to-many relationship between households and cooking systems</p> <p>household_id: Foreign key linking to the Household entity.</p> <p>cooking_system_id: Foreign key linking to the Cooking_System entity.</p>

6.3 Appendix 3: Risk and Mitigation Strategies

Risk	Impact	Mitigation Strategy
Hacking and Phishing Attacks	High	Employee training, multi-factor authentication (MFA), regular system updates, and penetration testing
Unauthorized data access	High	Implement strong access controls, encryption, regular audits, and continuous monitoring.
Data Loss or corruption	High	Implement a daily backup protocol. Use a redundant array of independent disks (RAID) storage systems.
Ransomware Attacks	Medium	Regular backups, network segmentation, and incident response planning
Insider threats	Medium	Implement the least privilege access, monitor user activities, and conduct regular security training
System Failure	Medium	Implement redundancy, regular system maintenance, and disaster recovery planning.
Theft of equipment	Medium	Remote device wiping capabilities and use of device encryption. Conduct personnel background checks
Natural Disasters	Low	Off-site data back-ups and an in-depth data recovery plan
Non-compliance with Data Protection Regulations	High	Regular compliance audits, appoint a Data Protection Officer (DPO), and provide compliance training

